

KonsortSWD Measure 5.1: metadata schema extended report

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Abstract (in German)

Persistente Identifikatoren (PIDs), die der Ebene der Attribute, z. B. einer Variable in sozialwissenschaftlichen Forschungsdaten, zugeordnet sind, erlauben es, Daten eindeutig zu zitieren und direkt abzurufen. Variablen können sich im Laufe der Zeit über Studienwellen hinweg ändern und PIDs fördern die Vernetzung über Erhebungswellen, Studien und andere Einheiten wie Fragen und Konzepte in Fragebögen. Angesichts der Bedeutung der Variablen und ihrer Verknüpfungen sollten die zugehörigen Metadaten solche Beziehungen dokumentieren und maschinell verwertbare Merkmale durch PIDs und kontrollierte Vokabulare umfassen. Die KonsortSWD-Maßnahme TA.5-M.1 Erweiterung der PID-Dienste als Basis für eine FAIR-Dateninfrastruktur" liefert eine PID-Registrierungserweiterung des dalra-Dienstes zur Vergabe von PIDs. Das grundlegende Metadatenschema wurde erweitert, um den steigenden Anforderungen an Interoperabilität, Datenmappings und Wissensgraphen gerecht zu werden. Diese Lösung umfasst ein Metadatenschema für die Identifizierung von persistenten Variablen und zur Speicherung von Querbeziehungen zwischen Variablen.

Abstract

The persistent identifiers (PIDs) assigned to the level of attributes, i.e., a variable in Social Science research data, can unambiguously cite and direct retrieve data. Variables change through the studies' timeline and promote cross-linking through the survey waves, studies, and other entities such as questions and concepts among questionnaires. Given the importance of variables and their ties, the associated metadata has to register such relations and allow machine actionable features through PIDs and controlled vocabulary terms. The KonsortSWD "Measure TA.5-M.1 Enhancing PID services as a base for a FAIR data infrastructure" outputs a PID registration widening of the dalra service to assign PIDs. The basic metadata schema was extended to meet the increasing demand for interoperability, data mappings, and knowledge graph. This solution comprises a metadata schema for the persistent variables identification and cross-linking relations.

Keywords:

Persistent Identifiers - PIDs. Research data citation. Research data - Social Sciences. Variables - Social Sciences. Granularity level identification. Research data services - technical infrastructure. Metadata schema.

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1. Introduction

The KonsortSWD “Measure TA.5–M.1 Enhancing PID services as a base for a FAIR data infrastructure” is a widening *da.ra*¹ service aiming to assign small-scale PIDs to the level of attributes, here as a first approach, a variable in Social Science research data. PIDs assigned to these attributes are individual elements of the data files that can be unambiguously referenced and allow straight data retrieval with the required metadata as a machine-actionable feature.

The first report² of the extended service provided the PID registration service requirements, such as the minimal metadata schema and the envisioned architecture to assign a PID to the entities (variables) within a dataset. To register a variable and get a PID, minimum metadata is necessary, such as the entity (variable) name, variable label, and the corresponding study DOI, along with the standard metadata fields, e.g., published or creator. Further documentation, such as the question, answers/responses schema, or descriptive fields within DDI (Data Documentation Initiative, 2020), is not necessary to obtain a PID. However, the metadata schema is now extended to meet the increasing demand for interoperability, data mappings (i.e., translation between machine-readable formats), and some particularities of the variable entity. The metadata schema then requires an extension to accommodate variable versions and their differences, a range of relations among variables through the survey waves, studies, and other entities such as questions, constructs or concepts in a given questionnaire.

The following section (2) describes some variable particularities, i.e., variable’s changing and their cross-linking. Section 3 presents the basic metadata schema properties and the metadata fields incorporated to extend the schema. Section 4 brings the metadata extended fields definition, and the terms of values controlled lists selected. Section 5 envisions future work, as the Social Sciences Knowledge Graph and section 6 discuss the results.

2. Variables changing and their cross-linking

Variables are an essential entity that frames data in social science research. Studies often use many variables, assigned with numbers and values, which carry meaningful information for investigation purposes. The variable values represent information on facts observed, people’s opinions and preferences, and a range of content, usually scored or ranked to promote relevant results from its qualitative or quantitative analysis.

¹ <https://www.da-ra.de>

² Klas, Claus-Peter, Zloch, Matthäus, Bach, Janete Saldanha, Baran, Erdal, & Mutschke, Peter. (2022). KonsortSWD Measure 5.1: PID Service for variables report (1.0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6397367>

Variables are organised as rectangular data, or datasets structured in columns³ and lines⁴, to properly allow its manipulation and inferences, favouring their application to the study objective. In this sense, the variable is the most relevant entity within the Social Sciences data framework or the researcher's target for reuse practices and secondary analysis. Considering that the variables are the entities that really provide information to the research situation in detail, revealing a phenomenon or behaviour which the social science researchers are dealing with, their role is central from the reuse standpoint. The variables provide a mass of data for the hypothesis's confirmation or refusal through variable interactions and their integrated analysis.

Variables can vary; their variation goes beyond the response dimension by individual cases in a survey response schema, for example. The value types such as numerals or range scales, free texts, or controlled vocabularies are also elements of the study design that forms the variable properties differentiation between one another. The variable properties also can take different attributes and values along studies' life cycles, panels, or survey waves. For instance, a given variable label is changed from one wave to another, even though its concept remains the same. Their values also are subject to change from one wave to another, such as new cardinalities settings, their categorization, or scale measurement. They change based on different conditions, e.g., values are updated by any constraints or modified to comply with the study evolution requirements; a new sociological approach is adopted, or the change is to fit the empirical reality in a constantly changing world.

To register a variable and get a PID, minimum metadata is necessary, such as name, label, and the corresponding study DOI, along with the standard metadata fields, e.g., published or creator. However, in order to provide connections within different but related variables, as exemplified earlier, the metadata schema designed to fulfil the PID registration service at *da.ra* was extended to address the variable versions and differences between related variables, i.e., to explicit relations among variables throughout waves, questions, questionnaires, and surveys. The related fields also encompass attribute values as PIDs or controlled vocabulary terms, which are machine-actionable features generating a visualisation in a knowledge map format.

The subsequent section describes how the PID registration service has its set of metadata extended to incorporate the relations among entities. We defined what types of relations make sense to connect into a network of variable relations. Following this approach, we provide different use cases on how variables connect with each other through relation fields and controlled vocabulary values.

3. Basic metadata schema and extension

The service was designed upon a metadata schema whose goal is to register the variable. The related metadata included the following properties to variable descriptions: Study DOI, entity name, entity label, PID Proposal, Landing Page, Resource type, Title, Creators, Publisher, Publication date, Availability, and Description/ Abstract. The mandatory or optional metadata fields depend on the PID standard; those required for assigning any PID or the ones needed for

³ In a data file, a single vertical column, each being one byte in length. Fixed-format data files are traditionally described as being arranged in lines and columns. In a fixed format file, column locations describe the locations of variables. (<https://www.icpsr.umich.edu/web/ICPSR/cms/2042>)

⁴ In general, a "line" in data file terminology refers to a physical unit of data that the computer reads and processes, one at a time. (<https://www.icpsr.umich.edu/web/ICPSR/cms/2042>)

the DOI standard is detailed in the service design report⁵. These properties are essential to identify the individual variable instance. To link variables with other related variables and, in the future, with other resource types, the metadata schema was extended, including the information sources identification and its relations fields.

The TA5-M1 team stayed focused on a minimal metadata schema necessary only to register the entity, starting with variable type, while keeping the schema brief and generic but applicable to more than one PID system, e.g., DOI and Handle system and also envisioning the registration of other entities types beyond variable (e.g., survey questions, response scale, audio/video data fragments, transcript excerpts). Since the variables do not speak for themselves but are always related to a study, detailed subject descriptions were not included as this information is available at the study level. The core metadata was then extended with related fields with properties RelatedIdentifier with relationType provided in the schema. It can also be slightly modified to cover new entities such as questions or specific data types, i.e., qualitative data files.

a. Overview

According to the PID registration service, basic metadata schema⁶ sets the metadata fields f as mandatory or optional depending on the PID system, those required for assigning any PID or the ones needed for the DOI standard.

Table 1 provides an overview of the PID registration schema's properties and semantics. Column 3 in the table indicates whether the property is Required and must-have information for the metadata validation within the PID registration service. The DataCite level of obligation is also informed in column 4, such as Mandatory (M), the property is obligatory; Recommended (R), the property is useful and should be added; and Optional (O), the property may be added.

ID	FIELD NAME	DESCRIPTION	PID SERVICE LEVEL OF REQUIREMENT	DATACITE LEVEL OF OBLIGATION	KNOWLEDGE GRAPH POTENTIAL METADATA FIELDS / SUBFIELDS
1	Study DOI*	A DOI or any PID: The DOI identifies the study in which the variable to register appears.	Required for any PID Required for DOI Standard	Mandatory (M) (with mandatory type sub-property) Identifier_Type	Persistent Identifiers (PIDs) for objects and research outputs ⁷
2	Entity Name	The name of the variable to register In this case, a variable.	Required for any PID	Optional (O)	
3	Entity Label	The label of the variable to register, In this case, a variable.	Required for any PID	Optional (O)	
4	PID Proposal*	The PID proposal of the variable to register. The PID can either be generated automatically or	Optional	Optional (O)	PID syntax

⁵ Klas, Claus-Peter, Zloch, Matthäus, Bach, Janete Saldanha, Baran, Erdal, & Mutschke, Peter. (2022). KonsortSWD Measure 5.1: PID Service for variables report (1.0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6397367>

⁶ Klas, Claus-Peter, Zloch, Matthäus, Bach, Janete Saldanha, Baran, Erdal, & Mutschke, Peter. (2022). KonsortSWD Measure 5.1: PID Service for variables report (1.0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6397367>

⁷ Digital Object Identifiers (DOIs), Archival Resource Key identifiers (ARKs), the Handle system (governed by the independent Swiss DONA Foundation and used by DOI, ePic and many other service providers), International Generic Sample Number (IGSNs), Uniform Resource Name (URN), Persistent Uniform Resource Locators (PURL), Research Activity identifier (RAiD), Research resource identifiers (RRID), Uniform Resource Identifier (URI), and Universally Unique Identifiers (UUID).

		provided by the user. The proposal is not mandatory but is recommended. Each institution registering variables can have a specific prefix and provide a proposal for registering the variable. The PID syntax will automatically be assigned if the proposal is not provided.			<doi_Proposal>Your prefix/Your suffix</doi_Proposal>
5	Landing Page*	The (URL) landing page of the variable to register, via which a user may obtain detailed information about the variable to register.	Required for any PID Required for DOI standard	Optional (O)	URL Adresse
6	Resource type*	The type of the resource, In this case, a variable.	Required for any PID Required for DOI standard registration	Mandatory (M) (with mandatory general type description sub-property)	Controlled List Values
7	Title	The title of the resource to register, which is generated by the registration service using the entity name and the entity label	Required for any PID Required for DOI standard	Mandatory (M) (with optional type sub-properties)	
8	Creators	The creators of the variable to register. The creators are the main researchers involved. Note the creators may be different from that of the study. Multiple entries are possible. It may be a corporate/institutional or personal name.	Required for any PID Required for DOI standard	Mandatory (M)	
9	Publisher	The name of the entity that holds, archives, publishes prints, distributes, releases, issues, or produces the Resource	Required for any PID Required for DOI standard	Mandatory (M)	
10	Publication date YYYY-MM-DD	The date of the publication of the study in which the variable to register appears	Required for any PID Required for DOI standard	Mandatory (M)	
11	Availability	The conditions governing the access to the resource: download, access under contract, open access, login required, etc..	Required for any PID Required for DOI standard	-	
12	Description/ Abstract	All additional information that does not fit in any of the other categories	Optional	Recommended (R)	

Table 1: Basic metadata schema to register a PID.

The basic metadata schema presented in table 1 provides some potential metadata fields for the knowledge graph generation. For instance, the Study DOI*, the PID Proposal*, the Landing Page*, and the Resource type* are metadata fields whose values are either PIDs, URLs or controlled vocabularies terms. Since these values type embedded machine-actionable features, they can be applied to build knowledge graph visualisation.

The PID syntax is based on the Handle system, so the PID proposal is a flexible value and allows the Institutions to register a prefix to personalise the PIDs. The Handle standard is a < PREFIX > / < SUFFIX > string (e.g. 11239/123456745). In the <prefix>/<suffix> syntax, the structure is commonly used to represent the Research Data Repository as a prefix. The suffix can represent a dataset or adopts a random number instead. The syntax also supports adding fragment

identifiers or a fragment-id, a small identification unit after < SUFFIX >. In this case, the syntax structure is < PREFIX > / < SUFFIX > # < fragment-id >. The syntax will be automatically generated if the data holder does not provide a PID Proposal. Some examples of the syntax < PREFIX > / < SUFFIX > # < fragment-id > are listed in table 2. As a matter of example only, the following syntax identification is provided: **dataProvider ID** as a < PREFIX >, *instrumentName* as < SUFFIX > and the *variableName* as < fragment-id >: i.e., <dataProvider>/<instrumentName>#<variableName>. PID Proposals listed in table 2 are all fictitious and provided as mere examples. They do not represent any PID syntax assigned to any data holder, dataset, or variable.

Handle system supported Syntax	< PREFIX > /	< SUFFIX > /	< fragment-id >
Surveys examples ⁸	<dataProvider>/	<instrumentName>#	<variableName>
ALLBUS ⁹	10.4232	allbus	pa02a
PID proposal	<10.4232>/<allbus>#<pa02a>		
ESS ¹⁰	10.21338	ess	polintr
PID proposal	<10.21338>/<ess>#<polintr>		
GPANEL ¹¹	10.4232	gpanel	caav068a
PID proposal	<10.4232>/<gpanel>#<caav068a>		
ISSP ¹²	10.4232	issp	V46
PID proposal	<10.4232>/<issp>#<V46>		
SOEP ¹³	10.5684	soep	bp75
PID proposal	<10.5684>/<soep>#<bp75>		
SOEP	10.5684	soep	cp75
PID proposal	<10.5684>/<soep>#<cp75>		

Table 2: PID proposal examples

Beyond the primary fields, the schema was extended to encompass relations among entities, in the first phase, the variables. The following section presents the supplementary metadata fields and their properties.

⁸ German General Social Survey - (ALLBUScompact), European Social Survey - (ESS), GESIS Panel - Standard Edition (GPANEL), International Social Survey Programme: Role of Government II - (ISSP, 1990), and The Socio-Economic Panel (SOEP).

⁹ GESIS - Leibniz-Institut für Sozialwissenschaften (2021). German General Social Survey (ALLBUScompact) - Cumulation 1980-2018. *GESIS Data Archive, Cologne. ZA5277 Data file Version 1.1.0*, <https://doi.org/10.4232/1.13775>.

¹⁰ <https://ess-search.nsd.no/CDW/ConceptVariables>

¹¹ GESIS (2022). GESIS Panel - Standard Edition. *GESIS, Cologne. ZA5665 Data file Version 43.0.0*, <https://doi.org/10.4232/1.13880>.

¹² ISSP Research Group (1992). International Social Survey Programme: Role of Government II - ISSP 1990. *GESIS Data Archive, Cologne. ZA1950 Data file Version 1.0.0*, <https://doi.org/10.4232/1.1950>

¹³ Socio-Economic Panel (SOEP), data for years 1984-2019, *SOEP-Core v36*, EU Edition, 2021, doi:10.5684/soep.core.v36eu

4. Metadata extended field definition and controlled vocabulary.

The related fields use controlled vocabularies and are machine-actionable features, generating a visualisation in a knowledge map format. The extended metadata fields are proposed to address the variable resource type particularities, i.e., relations that occur within the variables.

The relation metadata fields are:

- Related_Item
 - Related_Item_Identifier;
 - Related_Item_Identifier_Type;
 - Relation_Type

The extended metadata fields are proposed to address the variable resource type. The first extended metadata is the Related_Item, which is the resource type, i.e. the variable. The Related_Item has to have an identifier; therefore, a Related_Item_Identifier metadata field is set to provide the resource type identifier, preferred a PID or a controlled vocabulary term. Once the item Related to the variable (Related_Item) has an identifier (Related_Item_Identifier), then what type of that identifier needs to be described (Related_Item_Identifier_Type). This is important because various PID systems have different syntax and content. The metadata that provides the semantics on relationships between the two variables is the Relation_Type. This metadata aims to describe what kind of relation connects the registered variable with the identified target variable.

Table 3 shows the relations metadata fields useful for knowledge graph outputs, i.e., the fields in which the values are standardised information, such as PIDs or controlled vocabularies and can be machine-actionable to generate a visualization in a knowledge map format.

ID	FIELD NAME	DESCRIPTION	PID SERVICE LEVEL OF REQUIREMENT	DATACITE LEVEL OF OBLIGATION	KNOWLEDGE GRAPH EXTENDED METADATA FIELDS / SUBFIELDS
13	RelatedItem	The related resource (B)	Optional	Recommended (R)	Controlled List Values: resourceType: Variable
13.1	RelatedIdentifier (12)	PIDs - The format is dependent upon scheme	Optional	Recommended (R) (with RelatedIdentifier_Type and Relation_Type)	PID
13.1.1	RelatedIdentifier_Type (12.a)	Any PID system Depend on the Scheme	Optional	Recommended (R)	PID system name
13.1.2	Relation_Type (12.b)	Description of the relationship between the registered resource (A) and the target related resource (B)	Optional	If RelatedIdentifier is used, relationType is mandatory (M).	Controlled List Values: -IsContinuedBy -Continues -Describes -HasVersion -IsVersionOf -IsNewVersionOf -IsPreviousVersionOf -IsDocumentedBy -IsCompiledBy -IsVariantFormOf -IsDerivedFrom -IsSourceOf -IsRequiredBy -IsObsoletedBy

Table 3: Proposed [extended](#) metadata fields for registering a variable.

Table 4 simulates the variable's registration information. It includes the knowledge graph-related fields, i.e., the fields in which information are PIDs standards or controlled vocabularies (See relation one and relation two). All metadata values below are intended to be as an example of information that an institution registering a PID will provide for a given variable:

ID	FIELD NAME	EXAMPLE 1	EXAMPLE 2
1	Study DOI*	https://doi.org/10.34878/2019.01.dzhw_brief	https://doi.org/10.34878/2019.01.dzhw_brief
2	Entity Name	<u>ziwahr01</u>	<u>ziwahr02</u>
3	Entity Label	<i>Get a vocational training or study place for my desired profession</i>	<i>Make or design beautiful things</i>
4	PID Proposal ¹⁴	<u>21.T11998/dzhw-ziwahr01</u>	<u>21.T11998/dzhw-ziwahr02</u>
5	Landing Page*	https://www.dzhw.eu/ziwahr01	https://www.dzhw.eu/ziwahr02
6	Resource type*	<i>Variable</i>	<i>Variable</i>
7	Title	<i>Das Student Life Cycle Panel – Datenbasis für Forschung und Hochschulpolitik</i>	<i>Das Student Life Cycle Panel – Datenbasis für Forschung und Hochschulpolitik</i>
8	Creators	<i>Jungbauer-Gans, M., Carstensen, J.</i>	<i>Jungbauer-Gans, M., Carstensen, J.</i>
9	Publisher	<i>DZHW</i>	<i>DZHW</i>
10	Publication date	<i>2019</i>	<i>2019</i>
11	Availability	<i>Download</i>	<i>Download</i>
12	Description/ Abstract	The variable is part of Student Life Cycle Panel Oriented to the phases and transitions in the educational process and it investigates the probability of achieving career goals six months before graduation from high school	The variable is part of Student Life Cycle Panel Oriented to the phases and transitions in the educational process and it investigates the probability of achieving career goals six months before graduation from high school
13	RelatedItem	Variable	Variable
13.1	RelatedIdentifier	21.T11998/dzhw-ziwahr00	https://doi.org/10.4232/1.13737
13.1.1	RelatedIdentifier_Type	PID	DOI
13.1.2	Relation_Type	IsNewVersionOf	IntersectionOf
	<i>Definition</i>	<i>The registering variable (Variable A) is the new version of another variable, identified with PID 21.T11998/dzhw-ziwahr00.</i>	<i>The registering variable (Variable A) is constructed/dependent by two or more variables B & C, e.g., by crosstab with other variables such as Gender, Educational Background, or School type.</i>

Table 4: Metadata schema example for variables registration

¹⁴ PID Proposal: all PID proposals are fictitious and provided as mere examples. They do not represent any PID syntax assigned to any data holder, dataset, or variable.

The extended metadata fields are proposed to address the variable resource type particularities, i.e., relations that occur within the variables' perspective. However, Relation_Type detailed descriptions that can provide a semantic comprehension of variable ties are not available. In this sense, we propose an extended Relation_Type explanation for the Social Sciences domain and extend the resource types (i.e., questions, scales, scripts), which can be related to the variables in any way.

5. Future work

The variable entity relationships require an extension and detailed descriptions, capable of explaining and aligning the Relation_Type concept when applied to a variable. The conceptual alignment for Relation_Type values is relevant for controlled vocabulary purposes, so their adoption can be harmonised according to institutes and interested parties. The range of relations among variables through the survey waves, different studies, and other entities, such as questions and concepts in a given questionnaire, can not be understood equally by all researchers, users, and data curators. Thus providing such descriptions can improve the semantic comprehension of their ties. Such structure favours network interlinking comprehension, a base for the Social Sciences Knowledge Graph building.

Also, we propose to describe the Knowledge graph's relations with the variable and other entities. We define what types of connections make sense to assemble into a network of elements, considering what kind of elements better relate to variables. For instance, it is inherent to a variable that connects with a question. Following this approach, we intend to provide different use cases on how a variable connects with other entities, such as:

- A Paper or a DataPaper in which the variable is cited/published;
- The survey question that uses the variable;
- Relationships with other variables from different studies;
- The scales representing the variable answers;
- A landing page where metadata explaining the variable is available;
- An Interactive resource (a code, a script) that runs using the variable;
- A data management plan that envisions the variable, or;
- AV data (audio and video data) where a given variable could be represented.

Widening the graph relations with other entities, using controlled list values from resource types description, keeps the knowledge graph interoperable within other domains.

6. Conclusion

The PID registration service at *da.ra* aims to extend the current process, which assigns a PID only to a dataset or a study. It will include a PID at a lower granularity level, such as assigning PID to the variables within a dataset. It allows unambiguously citing the data and access to the variable (meta)-data individually through a landing page. Even though a core metadata schema is designed, extend the schema to metadata fields to register relations that align with FAIR terms. Since entities are connected with their related items, it favours a broader overview of the interdependent ties between them. That promotes findability, accessibility, interoperability, and future reuse.

Digital objects, such as variables and related entities (i.e. survey questions, responses scales, audio/video data fragments, etc.), could be brought together and improve metasearch and meta browsing, making it easier to find and access data. Also, it promotes a better harmonisation within variables, an expensive, time-consuming task. The measures to make inline data objects uniquely identified with a PID, along with explicit their relations through controlled vocabulary terms, then foster machine-actionable data features, strengthening the findability and enhancing data's reusability at the variables' level.

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